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How Literary Texts Cultivate Critical Thinking in Russian Language Lessons

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***Abstract:** This article examines the problems of developing critical thinking in Russian language lessons through the use of literary texts. The main focus is on working with literary works, which serve as a platform for the development of analytical skills, the ability to independently evaluate and interpret, as well as the formation of reasoned criticism. The article offers specific methods of working with texts, including higher-order questions, discussions, role-playing games and critical analysis. The results of the study can be used by teachers of the Russian language and literature to enrich the educational environment and improve the quality of education.*

***Key words:** development of critical thinking, fiction, Russian language, influence, techniques, role-playing games.*

Introduction. Cultivating critical thinking skills is a key component of the modern educational process, and its importance in teaching Russian cannot be overestimated. While learning Russian students should receive not only knowledge about the structure of the language, such as grammar and vocabulary, but also develop the ability to deeply analyze, critically evaluate and interpret various types of texts – from poetic to prose. The importance of critical thinking in linguistic education is increasing due to the need for students to develop the ability to think independently, highlight the main thing, build logical chains and develop the skill of reasoned discussion.

In Russian language lessons, the learning process is organized in such a way that students are not limited to reproductive activities, but move on to creative ones, where they learn to express their thoughts, argue them and defend their point of view. This approach contributes to the formation of students' evaluative attitude to language, teaches them to see deeper meanings and contexts behind words and phrases.

Working with literary texts plays a special role in the development of critical thinking. Literary works often contain many levels of meaning and provide rich material for analysis. Students learn not only to identify the main theme or plot twist, but also to understand the motives of the characters, to capture their psychological portraits, to reflect on the philosophical and moral and ethical issues raised by the author. The task of the teacher is to help students immerse themselves in the inner world of the work, reveal the author's intention and teach them to express their own vision and interpretation of what they read in a reasoned manner.

Mastery of critical thinking skills makes the learning process active and meaningful. Learning becomes not just the memorization of rules and facts, but the acquisition of vital competencies that contribute to a more conscious and responsible attitude to the information space around us. Ultimately, this contributes to the education of literate, thinking and socially active citizens capable of productive social interaction and self-realization.

A literary review. One of the fundamental studies in this field is the work of Klimov T.V. "Ways of forming a student's critical thinking" (2012)¹, which examines various strategies and techniques that can be used in the educational process to develop students' critical thinking. The author emphasizes the importance of integrating critical thinking into the educational process and highlights effective methods of its formation.

Kluster D. in the work "What is critical thinking?" (2005)² highlights the definition of critical thinking and its role in modern education. The author offers his own view on the techniques and methods that can be used to develop thinking skills, emphasizing the importance of new types of literacy.

Lukyanenko N.I. in the methodological manual "Techniques for the development of critical thinking in Russian language and literature lessons" (2016)³ refers to specific methods that are directly applicable in educational practice. He presents a toolkit for teachers that includes various techniques for working with texts aimed at developing critical thinking.

Alexandrova L. B. in the work "The use of literary texts for the development of analytical skills of students" (2022)⁴ focuses on the analysis of literary texts. The author argues that systematic analysis of literature promotes the development of critical thinking and improves students' understanding of complex ideological and philosophical concepts.

Petrova E. G. and Smirnova M. I. in their work "Interactive approaches to the development of thinking in the school literature course"⁵ (2022) explore the use of interactive technologies for the analysis of literary works. They note that involving students in interactive exercises contributes to a deeper understanding of the text and the development of argumentative skills.

¹ Климова, Т.В. Способы формирования критического мышления студента / Т.В. Климова. // Вестник ОГУ. – 2012. – №2 с. 78–85.

² Клустер, Д. Что такое критическое мышление? / Д. Клустер // Критическое мышление и новые виды грамотности / Д. Клустер. – Москва: 2005. – с. 5-13.

³ Лукьяненко, Н.И. Приёмы технологии развития критического мышления на уроках русского языка и литературы: метод. пособие / Н.И. Лукьяненко. – Пермский край: [б. и.], 2016. – 32 с.

⁴ Александрова Л. Б. Использование художественных текстов для развития аналитических навыков учащихся. Казань: Современное образование, 2022.

⁵ Петрова Е. Г., Смирнова М. И. Интерактивные подходы к развитию мышления в школьном курсе литературы. Санкт-Петербург: Педагогика XXI, 2022.

The reviewed works demonstrate the desire of modern scientists and teachers to develop students' abilities to think independently, argumentatively and critically, which is the basis for successful adaptation in a rapidly changing world and a key factor in full-fledged personal development.

As a continuation of the research, we sought to define critical thinking in the context of teaching Russian, identify specific techniques and methods used to develop critical thinking when working with literary texts, as well as substantiate hypotheses about the impact of the use of literary texts on the development of students' critical thinking.

Discussion and result. Various techniques can be used to develop critical thinking in Russian language lessons using literary texts. There are a huge number of such techniques, and we can cite some of them:

Higher-order issues. When developing critical thinking in Russian language lessons using literary texts, higher-order issues play an important role. Such questions are aimed at stimulating a deep understanding of what has been read, an analysis of the motives of the characters' actions, an understanding of the author's position and the hidden meanings of the work.

1. Why did the author choose this particular plot? What problems and conflicts did he want to reflect?
2. How do the characteristics of the main characters reveal the author's idea? What inner experiences do they have?
3. What are the main themes and motives of the work? How are they related to eternal human values?
4. What artistic techniques does the author use for a more vivid and emotional impact on the reader?
5. What is the role of landscape and interior descriptions in revealing the ideological content of the text?

Discussion of such issues helps students to penetrate into the deeper meaning of a work of art, understand the author's position and express their own opinion. This contributes to the formation of critical text analysis skills and the development of creative thinking.

Text analysis. A thorough analysis of a literary text is a key element in the development of critical thinking in Russian language lessons. This approach helps students not only to perceive the work superficially, but to dive deeply into its content, understand the author's intention and interpret hidden meanings. When working with a literary text, it is important to pay attention to such aspects as the characteristics of the characters, their motives and experiences, features of composition and linguistic means, symbols and subtexts.

For example, when analyzing Ivan Bunin's short story "The Gentleman from San Francisco"⁶, students can explore how portrait and interior descriptions reveal the inner world of the main character, a rich American who came to rest at an Italian resort. Through the details of his appearance, clothes and surroundings, one can understand his arrogance, alienation from ordinary people and the futility of his pursuit of luxury and fame. In addition, students can analyze how the cross-cutting motives of the frailty of human life and the indifference of the world to an individual express the philosophical subtext of this work.

⁶ Бунин И. А. Господин из Сан-Франциско // Бунин И. А. Собрание сочинений: в 6 т. – Москва: Художественная литература, 1965. – Т. 3. – С. 5-30.

Another example is the analysis of Fyodor Tyutchev's poem "Silentium!"⁷. Here, students can focus on identifying artistic techniques by which the author conveys his thoughts about the inability to adequately express the inner world of a person in a word. The images of the "inexpressible", "silent" space, the contrast between the spiritual depth and the outer shell, the ambiguity of key symbols – all this can become the subject of careful consideration and interpretation when working with this lyrical masterpiece.

Discussions and debates. Discussions and debates are powerful techniques for developing critical thinking in Russian language lessons when working with literary texts. By involving students in a lively discussion of issues related to the works they have read, the teacher stimulates their cognitive activity, teaches them to argue their position and respect the opinions of others.

For example, when studying Fyodor Dostoevsky's novel *Crime and Punishment*⁸, you can organize a debate on the topic "Is Raskolnikov guilty?". Some students will defend the idea that the main character committed a moral crime by violating universal norms. Others will try to justify him by referring to difficult life circumstances and Raskolnikov's philosophical views. During such a discussion, students will better understand the motives and inner torments of the character, better understand the author's intention and develop their own judgment about the problems raised in the work.

Another example is the discussion of the ideological content of Alexander Ostrovsky's play "The Storm"⁹. At the same time, students can be offered a debatable question: "Is Katerina a tragic victim or is she partly responsible for her own death?". Some students will emphasize that Katerina became a hostage to the cruel mores of the "dark kingdom", others – that she herself could not resist her passions and weaknesses. Such an exchange of opinions will help the children to better understand the complex psychological portrait of the heroine and the ambiguity of the author's position in this work.

Character comparison. Comparing literary characters helps students to better understand their inner world, motives of behavior and their role in revealing the author's idea. For example, when studying the novel "Fathers and Children" by Ivan Turgenev, Arkady Kirsanov and Evgeny Bazarov can be compared¹⁰. Despite the fact that they hold similar liberal views, these characters sharply contrast with each other in temperament, life priorities and attitude towards others. Such a comparison allows students not only to better understand the characters of the heroes, but also to see how through their confrontation Turgenev reveals the collision of fathers and children, the clash of the old and the new in post-reform Russia.

Comparison of motives. The comparison of the key motives running through the artwork helps students identify its ideological and thematic core. For example, when analyzing Lermontov's poems "I go out alone on the road"¹¹ and "Duma"¹², one can trace how the motive of loneliness and

⁷ Тютчев Ф. И. Silentium! // Тютчев Ф. И. Полное собрание стихотворений. – Москва: Книжное издательство, 2000. – С. 158.

⁸ Достоевский Ф. М. Преступление и наказание: роман в 6 частях с эпилогом / Ф. М. Достоевский; под ред. В. Г. Базанова. – Москва: Наука, 1970. – 671 с.

⁹ Островский А. Н. Гроза: драма в 5 действиях / А. Н. Островский; под ред. А. В. Дмитриева. – Москва: Изд-во МГУ, 1984. – 96 с.

¹⁰ Тургенев И. С. Отцы и дети: роман / И. С. Тургенев; под ред. А. В. Суперанской. – Москва: АСТ; Астрель, 2001. – 382 с.

¹¹ Лермонтов М. Ю. Выхожу один я на дорогу // Лермонтов М. Ю. Избранная лирика. – Москва: Современник, 1981. – С. 46.

¹² Лермонтов М. Ю. Дума // Лермонтов М. Ю. Избранная лирика. – Москва: Современник, 1981. – С. 102.

disappointment in life is revealed through the contrast between the hope of finding spiritual harmony and the feeling of futility of all aspirations. Such a comparison of motives allows schoolchildren to better understand the philosophical content of the poet's lyrics, his reflections on the fate of a personality in a hostile, indifferent world.

The contrast of artistic techniques. The identification of contrasting artistic techniques used by the author contributes to a subtler understanding of the ideological and aesthetic content of the work. For example, when analyzing Gogol's novel "The Overcoat"¹³, one can compare detailed, almost grotesque descriptions of the appearance and life of "significant persons" with concise, almost sketchy outlines of the appearance of the main character Akaky Akakievich. This contrasting image highlights the social inequality, loneliness and invisibility of the "little man" in an official world riddled with formalism and callousness.

The contrast of the landscapes. The comparison of landscape sketches in a literary text can reveal deep semantic connections. For example, in Leo Tolstoy's novel War and Peace¹⁴, the contrast of the serene, idyllic nature of the Borodino field before the battle and its terrible, devastated appearance after the battle symbolizes the tragedy of the war and devastating effect of which on all living things. Such a comparison helps students to feel the scale of historical events, to understand the author's philosophy about the inevitability and ruinousness of military conflicts.

Role-playing games. Role-playing games are a powerful tool for developing critical thinking in Russian language lessons when working with literary texts. By immersing themselves in the role of literary heroes, students learn to empathize with them, understand their motives and inner feelings. This helps to gain deeper insight into the author's intention and actively comprehend the issues of the work.

For example, when studying Ostrovsky's play "The Thunderstorm"¹⁵, students can be invited to stage the scene of Katerina's explanation with Boris. Some students will play the role of Katerina, trying to overcome the torments of conscience and fear, while others will play the role of Boris, sincerely in love, but forced to hide his feelings. Living through these emotions, the students will better feel the drama of the situation and the tragic fate of the heroine.

Another example is a role-playing game where students imagine themselves as Rodion Raskolnikov from Dostoevsky's novel Crime and Punishment¹⁶. Trying to justify or condemn him, they will dive deeper into the character's philosophical reflections on the right of a strong personality to transgress moral norms for the sake of a "great goal". This practice will allow the children not only to better understand Raskolnikov's inner world, but also to form their own position on the problems raised by the author.

Creative writing. One of the most effective methods of developing critical thinking in Russian language lessons using literary texts is creative writing. Such tasks encourage students not just to retell the plot or describe the characters, but to reflect on the deeper meanings of the work, express their own

¹³ Гоголь Н. В. Шинель // Гоголь Н. В. Петербургские повести. – Ленинград: Художественная литература, 1984. – С. 139-212.

¹⁴ Толстой Л. Н. Война и мир: роман-эпопея в 4 т. / Л. Н. Толстой; под ред. Л. Н. Толстая и др. – Москва: Гослитиздат, 1955. – Т. 1-4.

¹⁵ Островский А. Н. Гроза: драма в 5 действиях / А. Н. Островский; под ред. А. В. Дмитриева. – Москва: Изд-во МГУ, 1984. – 96 с.

¹⁶ Достоевский Ф. М. Преступление и наказание: роман в 6 частях с эпилогом / Ф. М. Достоевский; под ред. В. Г. Базанова. – Москва: Наука, 1970. – 671 с.

interpretation and attitude to the problems raised by the author. For example, when studying Gogol's novel "The Overcoat"¹⁷, students can be invited to write an essay on the topic "Why can Akaky Akakievich's act be considered an act of heroic resistance?". Such a task will require the guys to thoughtfully analyze the inner world of the "little man" and understand the author's position.

Illustrating texts. Another creative task that develops critical thinking may be the creation of illustrations for the works being studied. By drawing key scenes or images, students not only demonstrate their understanding of the text, but also learn to see the deep symbols and metaphors hidden in the author's idea. So, when working with Tyutchev's poem "Silentium!"¹⁸, schoolchildren can create graphic compositions reflecting the idea of the impossibility of adequately expressing the inner world of a person in a word. Such creative activity contributes to the development of associative and imaginative thinking of students.

Theatrical productions. Another effective creative task in Russian language lessons using fiction is the preparation of theatrical productions based on the studied works. By embodying the characters' images in stage actions, students penetrate deeper into their inner world, understand the author's intention and learn to express their vision of the conflict of a play or story. Thus, when studying Ostrovsky's drama "The Storm", schoolchildren can stage key dialogues between Katerina and other characters in order to more vividly convey the tragedy of her situation and the author's philosophy about the ruinousness of moral absolutism.

Making assumptions. At the final stage, students formulate their own assumptions about the development of events in the work, the motives and actions of the characters, as well as the possible author's intention. They may use phrases such as "In my opinion ...", "I assume that ...", "Most likely ...". It is important that these predictions are based on a thorough analysis of the text, and not on subjective expectations or speculation. Such work develops the skills of critical thinking, logical reasoning and argumentation.

Conclusion. The development of critical thinking in Russian language lessons using literary texts is an important task of modern education. This allows not only to understand and analyze works of verbal art more deeply, but also forms valuable personal qualities in students – the ability to make independent judgments, the ability to argue their position, and respect the opinions of others.

The methodological techniques proposed in this article, such as working with higher-order issues, text analysis, discussions and debates, comparison and contrast, role-playing games, creative tasks, will help language teachers create an atmosphere of intellectual activity in their lessons, involving students in a deep understanding of literary works. This activity not only develops critical thinking, but also contributes to the formation of moral guidelines, aesthetic taste, imagination and creative abilities of students.

Using a variety of methodological techniques and creative tasks – from essays and illustrations to theatrical productions – will allow students not only to deepen their knowledge, but also to experience personal impressions, empathizing with the characters and reflecting on the problems raised in literary texts. This, in turn, will contribute to their harmonious spiritual development and formation as mature, responsible and cultured individuals.

¹⁷ Гоголь Н. В. Шинель // Гоголь Н. В. Петербургские повести. – Ленинград: Художественная литература, 1984. – С. 139-212.

¹⁸ Тютчев Ф. И. Silentium! // Тютчев Ф. И. Полное собрание стихотворений. – Москва: Книжное издательство, 2000. – С. 158.

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